

Coupled CFD-DEM simulation of pin-type wet stirred media mills using immersed boundary approach and hydrodynamic lubrication force

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

HIGHLIGHTS

- A coupled CFD-DEM framework to model the wet stirred media mills is presented.
- An immersed boundary methodology is used to emulate the stirrer rotation in CFD.
- Fluid interaction between grinding bead surfaces is modeled using lubrication force.
- The effect of process parameters on the system behavior is described.
- Water-glycerol mixture properties are used to analyze the fluid effect.

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ABSTRACT

Qualitative description of stressing energies between grinding beads/media in wet stirred media mills at different operation settings could provide a comprehensive understanding of the process parameter influence. In the current work, a modeling approach for wet stirred media mills is described, employing a coupled CFD-DEM framework. This study employs an immersed boundary methodology to emulate the pin-type stirrer rotation in CFD and utilizes a hydrodynamic lubrication force to model the squeezing out and sucking in of fluid between two grinding bead surfaces. The results indicate the influence of process parameters such as the stirrer rotation speed, bead diameter, and bead filling degree. Key findings include the necessity of coupled CFD-DEM with lubrication (i.e., comparison of results from DEM, and coupled CFD-DEM simulations). Dependence of system dynamics on the fluid properties is numerically analyzed using the properties of water-glycerol mixtures.

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1. Introduction

Wet-operated Stirred Media Mills (WSMMs) are essential systems in many industrial applications such as food, pharmaceuticals, and mineral processing [1–3]. Their functionality is to reduce the particle size of materials ranging from several millimeters down to less than a hundred nanometers. These systems are typically filled with grinding media, such as beads, and a slurry of the product material to be ground. The grinding beads and slurry are agitated by a high-speed stirrer, resulting in the collisions of grinding beads with one another and with the mill internals. These collisions drive the breakage phenomenon or the particle size reduction in the slurry, if the product particles are caught in between the collision partners. WSMMs have several advantages such as, the ability to produce very small particle sizes (down to the nanometer size range), as smaller grinding beads/media can be used, which yield high stress numbers. Also, one can induce stabilization to the product suspensions to minimize the particle–particle interactions, especially for sub-micron particle sizes, which in turn prevents an increase in viscosity and a resulting increase in pressure in the mill [4,5].

The main challenge here is to identify and set the effective operating state for a given situation i.e., either to minimize the specific energy consumption (which goes along with minimizing the product contamination by grinding media and mill wear) or maximizing the productivity (increase the throughput). The fact that there are a number of process parameters that might potentially affect the system (such as, bead size, filling degree, stirrer rotation speed, flow rate, mode of operation i.e., continuous or circuit mode, mill and stirrer design, etc.) to improve or control its performance makes it complicated to identify the right set of parameters. The effect of the aforementioned parameters can be assessed using experimental investigations [2,6,7] to set optimal operating points but it requires an extensive experimental work for such analysis. Also, the data produced with a certain machine is not transferable to a different machine configuration i.e., rotor (geometry, material), bead (material), etc.. Stender et al. [8], Kwade & Schwedes [2] provided scale-up rules to transfer the mean stress energy of a mill (with similar configurations) for different mill volumes (adopted in Flach et al. [9]), but such scale-up does not yield an accurate and quantitative description of stress energy distribution. Additionally, such scale-up is not suitable when the solids content, viscosity and the mill (and stirrer) design are varied simultaneously.

Numerical simulation tools such as Discrete Element Method (DEM) have been previously employed to track grinding bead trajectories and collisions for dry mills with different designs and at different scales [10–12]. In the case of wet systems, the DEM is coupled with either Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) [13–15], Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) [16–18], or the Particle Finite Element Method (PFEM) [19–21] to virtualize the real system i.e., the mill environment, and extract the necessary information. Numerical modeling gives a scope for virtual process engineering i.e., obtaining qualitative and quantitative information such as stress energy distribution, the spatial distribution of the grinding beads within different grinding and separation zones of the mill [22,23]. The main limitation of such modeling approach is that the presence of feed/product particles is not considered in the simulations due to their extremely high number. DEM presents a limit on the particle number that can be simulated as it directly affects the simulation run time [24,25]. However, with proper calibration regarding the product suspension rheological properties, the simulations can capture the grinding media motion pattern as well as the relative velocity, and stress energy distribution for a given set of process parameters, thereby enabling an understanding of the system dynamics for optimization and defining good practices.

Previous coupled CFD-DEM studies have addressed the modeling of disc or annular-gap type configurations of the stirrer [13,23,26], which have a consistent boundary force on the CFD mesh. Such configurations can be emulated by the single rotating frame or moving reference

frame approaches in CFD. Also, few studies have highlighted to incorporate the effect of particle dispersion in fluid using a hydrodynamic lubrication force [22] i.e., accounting for fluid interactions in DEM without coupling with CFD. Beinert et al. [27] have used the one-way coupled CFD-DEM simulations, along with a simplified displacement force (given by Davis and Serayssol [28]) in between the approaching grinding beads, to describe an annular-gap mill. The model underestimated the displacement force and the loss in kinetic energy. However, in their study, they observed significant differences in results for dry and wet-operated systems. Carvalho et al. [29] have used population balance modeling (PBM) aided with coupled CFD-DEM to predict the grinding in a pilot scale mill, in which they adjusted the coefficient of restitution of the contacts to assume the damping due to fluid presence.

In the present work, an immersed boundary (IB) method is used to emulate the stirrer rotation which was successfully applied and tested for the cases of stirred tank reactors with pitched blade turbines [30, 31]. Additionally, this study includes a hydrodynamic lubrication effect [32] to compensate for the lack of particle resolution in the unresolved CFD-DEM coupling approach [33].

This study advances previous research by enhancing the coupled CFD-DEM modeling of wet stirred media mills by incorporating an immersed boundary methodology and a hydrodynamic lubrication force, enabling more accurate modeling of fluid-particle interactions and complex stirrer geometries. Additionally, it provides a detailed numerical analysis of the impact of fluid properties on system dynamics and evaluates the influence of various process parameters on stress energy distribution and stress frequency. These contributions offer valuable insights for optimizing the operation of wet stirred media mills. A bench scale mill, with pin-type stirrer from Netzsch (MiniCer) was chosen as a geometrical model.

2. Model formulation

Coupled CFD-DEM modeling gives a continuous description of the fluid phase, coarser than that of the particulate scale, using the Volume-Averaged Navier Stokes (VANS) equations while the particulate phase is modeled using the Discrete Element Method (DEM), which tracks the motion of discrete entities (particulate phase). The CFD and DEM are operated independently with their respective governing equations, but are coupled at regular intervals (usually multiple DEM time steps for a single CFD time step). This section describes the governing equations for a coupled CFD-DEM framework that is used in the present work. The software packages used are LIGGGHTS [34], and CFDEMcoupling [35] (with OpenFOAM-6 [36]).

2.1. Governing equations for the solid-phase (DEM)

Governing equations of DEM are mainly based on the integration of Newton's second law, which tracks the positions and velocities of discrete entities that evolve in time, i.e., for the solid particulate phase. The inter-particle collisions are described using a soft sphere approach. In the soft sphere approach, particles undergo deformation during contact, and the contact forces are computed as simple spring, dash-pot, and slider analogues. DEM theory was introduced by Alder and Wainwright in 1956 for molecular dynamics (MD) studies and later developed by Cundall and Strack [37] to describe the mechanical behavior of assemblies of discs and spheres. In the present work, we solve the particle motion (translational and rotational) using an academic adaptation of the open-source implementation of LIGGGHTS [34].

According to Newton's second law, the following equations describe the translational (v_i) and rotational (ω_i) motions of a particle i :

$$m_i \frac{dv_i}{dt} = \sum_j f_{c,ij} + \sum_k f_{nc,ik} + f_{pf,i} + f_{g,i} \quad (1)$$

$$I_i \frac{d\omega_i}{dt} = \sum_j (M_{t,ij} + M_{r,ij}) \quad (2)$$

Table 1
Contact model equations.

Parameter	Equation
Normal stiffness	$k_{n,ij} = \frac{4}{3} Y_{ij}^* \sqrt{R_{ij}^* \delta_{n,ij}}$
Tangential stiffness	$k_{t,ij} = 8G_{ij}^* \sqrt{R_{ij}^* \delta_{n,ij}}$
Normal damping	$\gamma_{n,ij} = -2\sqrt{\frac{5}{6}} \frac{\ln(\epsilon)}{\sqrt{\ln^2(\epsilon) + \pi^2}} \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} k_{n,ij} m_{ij}^*}$
Tangential damping	$\gamma_{t,ij} = -2\sqrt{\frac{5}{6}} \frac{\ln(\epsilon)}{\sqrt{\ln^2(\epsilon) + \pi^2}} \sqrt{k_{t,ij} m_{ij}^*}$
Torque from tangential interaction	$\mathbf{M}_{t,ij} = \mathbf{r}_i \times (\mathbf{f}_{ct,ij})$
Rolling resistance torque	$\mathbf{M}_{r,ij} = -\mu_{s,ij} \mathbf{f}_{cn,ij} \frac{\omega_{ij}}{ \omega_{ij} } R_{ij}^*$
Effective mass	$\frac{1}{m_{ij}^*} = \frac{1}{m_i} + \frac{1}{m_j}$
Effective radius	$\frac{1}{R_{ij}^*} = \frac{1}{R_i} + \frac{1}{R_j}$
Effective Young's modulus	$\frac{1}{Y_{ij}^*} = \frac{(1-\nu_i^*)}{Y_i} + \frac{(1-\nu_j^*)}{Y_j}$
Effective shear modulus	$\frac{1}{G_{ij}^*} = \frac{2(2+\nu_i)(1-\nu_i)}{Y_i} + \frac{2(2+\nu_j)(1-\nu_j)}{Y_j}$
Sliding friction coefficient	$\mu_{s,ij}$
Rolling friction coefficient	$\mu_{r,ij}$
Distance to contact point for particle i	r_i
Radius of particle i	R_i

where m_i represents the mass of particle i , I_i is its moment of inertia, $\mathbf{f}_{c,ij}$ denotes the contact force(s) between particle i and particle j , $\mathbf{f}_{nc,ik}$ represents the non-contact forces between particle i and particle k , $\mathbf{f}_{pf,i}$ is the particle–fluid interaction forces, $\mathbf{f}_{g,i}$ signifies a body force like gravity. $\mathbf{M}_{t,ij}$ and $\mathbf{M}_{r,ij}$ are the tangential and rolling moments acting on particle i and particle j , respectively. In this work, we adopt a lubrication force (see Section 2.1.2) as a non-contact force, while the other non-contact forces, such as the electrostatic or van der Waals forces, are not considered, as they are orders of magnitude smaller than the hydrodynamic or contact forces for the particles (grinding beads) considered. The expression for the particle–fluid interaction force depends on the interactions considered (drag, lift, etc.) (see Section 2.3 for details).

Further, the contact force between two particles $\mathbf{f}_{c,ij}$ can be split into two components i.e., normal ($\mathbf{f}_{cn,ij}$) and tangential ($\mathbf{f}_{ct,ij}$) [38]. The resulting expressions are as follows:

$$\mathbf{f}_{c,ij} = \mathbf{f}_{cn,ij} + \mathbf{f}_{ct,ij} \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{f}_{c,ij} = -k_{n,ij} \delta_{n,ij} - \gamma_{n,ij} \dot{\delta}_{n,ij} - k_{t,ij} \delta_{t,ij} - \gamma_{t,ij} \dot{\delta}_{t,ij} \quad (4)$$

where $k_{n,ij}$ and $k_{t,ij}$ are the normal and tangential stiffness coefficients, respectively; $\gamma_{n,ij}$ and $\gamma_{t,ij}$ are the normal and tangential damping coefficients, respectively; $\delta_{n,ij}$ and $\delta_{t,ij}$ represent the normal and tangential particle overlaps, while $\dot{\delta}_{n,ij}$ and $\dot{\delta}_{t,ij}$ are their corresponding time derivatives.

2.1.1. Contact model

In the present work, we use a contact model based on the Hertz theory for the normal forces [39,40] and the Mindlin model for the tangential forces [41,42]. The adopted models utilize the material properties such as Young's modulus (Y), Poisson's ratio (ν) and coefficient of restitution (e) to describe the stiffness and damping parameters given in Eq. (4). The equations that are used to link the material properties to the coefficients in Eq. (4) are described in Table 1. Furthermore, the tangential overlap ($\delta_{t,ij}$) is limited by Coulomb's law to ensure,

$$|\mathbf{f}_{ct,ij}| \leq -\mu_{s,ij} |\mathbf{f}_{cn,ij}| \frac{\delta_{t,ij}}{|\delta_{t,ij}|} \quad (5)$$

2.1.2. Non-contact model

Grinding beads immersed in a fluid affect each other through lubrication forces [43]. These forces are relevant especially when two beads, approach towards each other. The lubrication forces originate from squeezing out or sucking in the fluid when particles approach and move away respectively. In this work, the lubrication forces are added in the DEM as a non-contact force model to emulate the near-particle hydrodynamic interactions between the fluid and beads (immersed in the fluid). For a viscous fluid, the lubrication interaction must be incorporated especially when a relatively coarse resolution for the fluid solver is adopted.

In the current work, a lubrication force model described by Kroupa et al. [32] is adopted. The lubrication forces for particle–particle and particle–wall interactions are described in Eqs. (6)–(9) and in Eqs. (10)–(13), respectively (according to Dance and Maxey [44]). The expressions assume that the flow between the two approaching bodies is in the Stokes' limit.

$$\mathbf{F}_{nl} = -6\pi\eta_f R_p \mathbf{v}_r \cdot \mathbf{n} \left(\frac{1}{4} \epsilon^{-1} - \frac{9}{40} \log \epsilon - \frac{3}{112} \epsilon \log \epsilon \right) \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{sl} = -6\pi\eta_f R_p \left[\mathbf{v}_s \left(-\frac{1}{6} \log \epsilon \right) + \mathbf{v}_{cs} \left(-\frac{1}{6} \log \epsilon - \frac{1}{12} \epsilon \log \epsilon \right) \right] \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{M}_{sl} = -8\pi\eta_f R_p^2 \left[(\mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{v}_s) \left(-\frac{1}{6} \log \epsilon - \frac{1}{12} \epsilon \log \epsilon \right) + (\mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{v}_{cs}) \left(-\frac{1}{5} \log \epsilon - \frac{47}{250} \epsilon \log \epsilon \right) \right] \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{M}_{tl} = -8\pi\eta_f R_p^2 [(\boldsymbol{\Omega}_i - \boldsymbol{\Omega}_j) \cdot \mathbf{n}] \mathbf{n} \left(\frac{1}{8} \epsilon \log \epsilon \right) \quad (9)$$

In the above equations, \mathbf{F}_{nl} , \mathbf{F}_{sl} , \mathbf{M}_{sl} , \mathbf{M}_{tl} are the normal force, sliding force, sliding torque, twisting torque respectively, between two equally sized particles. $\epsilon = \frac{h}{R_p}$ is the relative distance, with $h = |\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j| - 2R_p$ as the separation distance between particle surfaces, $\mathbf{v}_r = \mathbf{v}_i - \mathbf{v}_j$ is the relative velocity of particles i and j , \mathbf{n} is the unit normal vector pointing from the two centers of the particles. $\mathbf{v}_s = \mathbf{v}_r - (\mathbf{v}_r \cdot \mathbf{n}) \mathbf{n}$ is the sliding velocity due to translational motion. $\mathbf{v}_{cs} = \mathbf{v}_{c,i} - \mathbf{v}_{c,j}$ is the sliding velocity due to rotational motion, with $\mathbf{v}_{c,i} = \boldsymbol{\Omega}_i \times \mathbf{r}_i$ and $\mathbf{v}_{c,j} = \boldsymbol{\Omega}_j \times \mathbf{r}_j$ being the surface velocities due to the rotation at the point lying on the line connecting particle centres of particles i and j , respectively. And, $\mathbf{r}_i = R_p \mathbf{n}$ and $\mathbf{r}_j = -R_p \mathbf{n}$ are the vectors pointing from each particle's center to its surface.

$$\mathbf{F}_{nl}^w = -6\pi\eta_f R_p \mathbf{v}_r \cdot \mathbf{n} \left(\epsilon^{-1} - \frac{1}{5} \log \epsilon - \frac{1}{21} \epsilon \log \epsilon \right) \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{sl}^w = -6\pi\eta_f R_p \left[\mathbf{v}_s \left(-\frac{8}{15} \log \epsilon - \frac{64}{375} \epsilon \log \epsilon \right) + \mathbf{v}_{cs} \left(-\frac{2}{15} \log \epsilon - \frac{86}{375} \epsilon \log \epsilon \right) \right] \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{M}_{sl}^w = -8\pi\eta_f R_p^2 \left[(\mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{v}_s) \left(-\frac{2}{15} \log \epsilon - \frac{86}{375} \epsilon \log \epsilon \right) + (\mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{v}_{cs}) \left(-\frac{2}{5} \log \epsilon - \frac{66}{125} \epsilon \log \epsilon \right) \right] \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{M}_{tl}^w = -8\pi\eta_f R_p^2 [(\boldsymbol{\Omega}_i - \boldsymbol{\Omega}_j) \cdot \mathbf{n}] \mathbf{n} \left(\frac{1}{2} \epsilon \log \epsilon \right) \quad (13)$$

In the above equations, \mathbf{F}_{nl}^w , \mathbf{F}_{sl}^w , \mathbf{M}_{sl}^w , \mathbf{M}_{tl}^w are the normal force, sliding force, sliding torque, twisting torque respectively, between the particle and the wall. The relative velocity \mathbf{v}_r , the sliding velocity \mathbf{v}_s , and the sliding velocity due to the rotational motion \mathbf{v}_{cs} are evaluated similar to the particle–particle interaction, but only considering the wall as particle j with velocity and rotation rate as zero.

An issue with the above expressions to compute the lubrication forces is that when the collision velocity of particles $v \rightarrow 0$ and when $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$, the force calculation leads to $0 \cdot \infty$. To overcome this

divergent behavior of the lubrication forces, Kroupa et al. [32] adopted a correction factor f^* suggested by Vinogradova [45].

However, in the present work, we evaluate the lubrication forces only until a specified cut-off distance d_{cut} ; after that, we do not compute or take the lubrication forces into account, i.e., the lubrication forces are prevalent at $d_{cut} \leq h < d_{gb}$, where h is the surface distance between the mono-disperse beads i and j . In this case, we do not use the correction factor f^* .

2.2. Governing equations for the fluid-phase (CFD)

The incompressible Volume-Averaged Navier Stokes (VANS) equations considered in this work are adopted from the work of Zhou et al. [46]. The equations adopted are described as set II in Zhou et al. [46], which are given as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \epsilon_f}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\epsilon_f \mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\rho_f \epsilon_f \mathbf{u})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_f \epsilon_f \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u}) = -\epsilon_f \nabla p + \epsilon_f \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} + \rho_f \epsilon_f \mathbf{g} - \mathbf{F}_{pf} \quad (15)$$

where ϵ_f is the void fraction, ρ_f is the fluid density, \mathbf{u} is the velocity, \mathbf{g} is the gravity, and p is the pressure. The viscous tensor $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is given as:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \mu_f \left((\nabla \mathbf{u}) + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T - \frac{2}{3} (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) \boldsymbol{\delta}_k \right) \quad (16)$$

where μ_f is the dynamic viscosity and $\boldsymbol{\delta}_k$ is the identity tensor.

In Eq. (15), the term \mathbf{F}_{pf} is the momentum exchange term from particles to the fluid. It is given as:

$$\mathbf{F}_{pf} = \frac{1}{\Delta V} \sum_i^{n_p} \mathbf{f}_{pf,i} - \mathbf{f}_{\nabla p,i} - \mathbf{f}_{\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau},i} - \mathbf{f}_{Ar,i} \quad (17)$$

where,

$$\mathbf{f}_{pf,i} = \mathbf{f}_{d,i} + \mathbf{f}_{\nabla p,i} + \mathbf{f}_{\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau},i} + \mathbf{f}_{Ar,i} + \mathbf{f}_{vm,i} + \mathbf{f}_{B,i} + \mathbf{f}_{Saff,i} + \mathbf{f}_{Mag,i} \quad (18)$$

where n_p is the number of particles, ΔV is the volume of the cell in which a particle i is present and $\mathbf{f}_{pf,i}$ is the sum of all fluid-solid interaction forces that involve particle i . This term can be sub-divided into several contributions such as, drag $\mathbf{f}_{d,i}$, pressure gradient $\mathbf{f}_{\nabla p,i}$, shear or viscous stress $\mathbf{f}_{\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau},i}$, Archimedes or buoyant force $\mathbf{f}_{Ar,i}$, virtual mass $\mathbf{f}_{vm,i}$, Basset force $\mathbf{f}_{B,i}$, Saffman lift force $\mathbf{f}_{Saff,i}$, and Magnus lift force $\mathbf{f}_{Mag,i}$. The Pressure Implicit with Splitting of Operators (PISO) scheme [47] solves Eqs. (14) and (15).

2.3. Models for solid–liquid coupling strategy

In this work, only the drag, pressure gradient, viscous (shear), and Archimedes forces are taken into account and all other force calculations in Eq. (18) are ignored, as they are not relevant for the current case. The expressions for the force models adopted in current work are described in Table 2.

In the unresolved approach of CFD-DEM coupling [33], the particles are not discretized explicitly in the VANS equations. As described in Crowe et al. [48], the terms involving pressure gradient and the divergence of the shear stress are obtained by integrating the respective terms over the volume occupied by each of the particles in a cell. Koch-Hill drag model, which calculates the particle based drag force given by Koch & Hill [49] (as described by van Buijtenen et al. [50]) is adopted in this work. This model was tested and used in the modeling applications of wet stirred media mills [23,51].

Table 2

Expressions for the forces taken for the solid–liquid coupling strategy in CFD-DEM modeling. The expressions describe a particle i moving at velocity \mathbf{v}_i .

Force	Equation
Pressure gradient [38]	$-\frac{\pi}{6} d_p^3 \nabla p$
Viscous or shear [38]	$-\frac{\pi}{6} d_p^3 \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}$
Drag	$\frac{V_p \beta}{\epsilon_p} (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}_i)$
(Koch-Hill) [49] [50]	with $\beta = \frac{18\mu_f \epsilon_p^2}{d_p^2} \left(F_0(\epsilon_p) + \frac{1}{2} F_3(\epsilon_p) Re_p \right)$ where, $\epsilon_p + \epsilon_f = 1$ and $Re_p = \frac{\epsilon_f \rho_f \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}_i d_p}{\mu_f}$
	$F_0(\epsilon_p) = \begin{cases} 1 + 3\sqrt{\frac{2\epsilon_p}{\pi} + \frac{15}{\pi^2} \epsilon_p \ln(\epsilon_p)} + 16.14\epsilon_p, & \text{if } \epsilon_p < 0.4 \\ \frac{10\epsilon_p}{\epsilon_f^2}, & \text{if } \epsilon_p \geq 0.4 \end{cases}$
	$F_3(\epsilon_p) = 0.0673 + 0.212\epsilon_p + \frac{0.0232}{\epsilon_f^2}$
Archimedes	$\mathbf{g}(\rho_f - \rho_p) V_p$

2.3.1. Void fraction and momentum exchange

The CFD and DEM are coupled with each other i.e., a two-way coupling approach is adopted in the current work. The volume of particles and the solid-to-fluid forces are projected on to the finite volume (FV) mesh to compute the void fraction ϵ_f and the momentum exchange term \mathbf{F}_{pf} . A ‘divided’ approach of the CFDEM framework [33,35,52] is chosen, to avoid the potential instabilities in the evaluation of ϵ_f and \mathbf{F}_{pf} and to conserve mass when a grid size $\Delta x < 3d_p$ is chosen [53,54].

Eq. (19) adds the momentum exchange force term, making it more suitable for implicit coupling strategies and avoids adding it explicitly, as shown in Eq. (15).

$$\frac{\partial (\rho_f \epsilon_f \mathbf{u})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_f \epsilon_f \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u}) = -\epsilon_f \nabla p + \epsilon_f \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} + \rho_f \epsilon_f \mathbf{g} + K_{pf} (\mathbf{u}_p - \mathbf{u}) \quad (19)$$

where \mathbf{u}_p is the average particle velocity in a corresponding grid cell and K_{pf} is a scalar used to scale the magnitude of the momentum exchange force. It is given as:

$$K_{pf} = \frac{|\mathbf{F}_{pf}|}{|\mathbf{u}_p - \mathbf{u}|} \quad (20)$$

2.3.2. Smoothing of the void fraction and momentum exchange fields

On top of the divided approach, a smoothing model is chosen to smear the void fraction and the momentum exchange forces on the neighboring cells. This additional step is performed to stabilize the particle-fluid coupling. Isotropic diffusive smoothing, reported by Pirker et al. [54] is adopted (see Eq. (21)).

$$\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial t} = \nabla^2 \left(\frac{\lambda^2}{\Delta t_{CFD}} \xi \right) \quad (21)$$

where λ is the characteristic smoothing length and Δt_{CFD} is the time step employed to solve the VANS Eqs. (14) and (15). This conservative smoothing method can be controlled using the smoothing length λ .

2.3.3. Stirrer motion

There are several methodologies for realizing the motion of rotating bodies in CFD. The methodologies include the sliding mesh (SM), multiple reference frame (MRF) and the single rotating frame (SRF). However, each of these methodologies suffer from limitations in terms of the type of geometries that they can handle and their capability to solve steady or unsteady problems [55]. On the other hand, immersed boundary (IB) and fictitious domain (FD) approaches serve as alternatives for the aforementioned methods, as they can handle complex geometries and can be easily implemented in parallel to achieve computational efficiency. Moreover, they can be used in the applications with multiple impellers and situations with overlapping swept volumes and can handle 6 degrees of freedom of geometry movement.

In the present work, the stirrer movement is emulated using a semi-implicit immersed boundary (IB) approach, implemented within pressure implicit with splitting of operators (PISO) scheme, termed as

Fig. 1. A 2D illustration of the cell center and vertex flagging method.

PISO-IB that was introduced by Blais et al. [31]. They extended the approach to couple DEM (with CFD) to model solid–liquid mixing [30]. This method was integrated within the CFDEM framework [33,35,52], and it can handle unstructured meshes. It requires the surface mesh of a moving object to describe its motion within the computational domain and can be used with static mesh or dynamic mesh refinement.

The basic idea of the PISO-IB approach is to determine the moving geometry on the computational domain using a cell center and vertex flagging method. The surface mesh, i.e., an STL file in this case, projects onto the finite volume (FV) mesh by generating a Boolean list that indicates which cell centers and vertices of the FV mesh intersect with the given surface mesh. Fig. 1 illustrates the cell center and vertex detection technique, that creates two lists called fluid and solid nodes (in white and gray regions respectively). Thereby a solid fraction for each cell i is generated using:

$$\beta_i = \frac{N_{vc,i} + N_{cc,i}N_{v,i}}{2N_{v,i}} \quad (22)$$

where $N_{v,i}$ is the number of vertices in cell i (e.g., 8 for a hexahedron), $N_{vc,i}$ and $N_{cc,i}$ are the number of vertices and centers intersecting the immersed body, respectively.

The following equation defines the velocity of cell i that intersects the immersed body:

$$\mathbf{u}_{ib,i} = \mathbf{v}_{ib} + \frac{1}{N_{vc,i} + N_{v,i}} \left[\left[\sum_j^{N_{vc,i}} \boldsymbol{\omega} \times (\mathbf{x}_{v,j} - \mathbf{x}_{ib}) \right] + N_{v,i} \boldsymbol{\omega} \times (\mathbf{x}_{c,i} - \mathbf{x}_{ib}) \right] \quad (23)$$

where, $\mathbf{u}_{ib,i}$ represents the velocity of the cell i , \mathbf{v}_{ib} is the body's translational velocity, \mathbf{x}_{ib} its center of rotation, $\mathbf{x}_{c,i}$ and $\mathbf{x}_{v,j}$ are the coordinates of its center and vertices, respectively.

In this approach, the volume of the projected body may not be exactly the same as the volume of the corresponding surface mesh. Therefore, a so-called halo layer that corresponds to the cells i in which the solid (body) fraction $\beta_i \in]0, 1[$, is shrunk or expanded to correct the volume of the discretized immersed body. Further details about the numerical implementation of the underlying schemes and method validation for single-phase mixing can be found in Blais et al. [31].

Table 3

Details of a bench scale, pin-type wet stirred media mill, MiniCer from Netzsch.

Parameter	Value
Stirrer volume	$5.245 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^3$
Active volume (for bead filling)	$2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3$
Bead diameter(s)	0.1–2 mm
Outlet diameter	0.02 m
Distance from center of rotation to the stirrer tip	0.0295 m

3. Methodology

3.1. Geometry

The geometry of a bench-scale, pin-type wet stirred media mill, MiniCer from Netzsch is considered for the present work. The geometries of the grinding chamber and the stirrer (in .stl format) are generated using Autodesk Inventor 2022. The 3-dimensional representations of the grinding chamber and the stirrer are shown in Fig. 2. The details about the mill are given in Table 3. Both the grinding chamber and the stirrer are made with ceramic material (Zirconium Oxide - ZrO_2).

3.2. Simulation setup

As described in Section 2, the academic implementations of LIGGGHTS [34], OpenFOAM-6 [36], and CFD-DEM coupling [35] are used to simulate the wet stirred media mill system, this section focuses on a detailed overview on setting up the simulations, modeling parameters and the assumptions taken.

Each simulation case is implemented in three stages: initialize, stabilize, and run. The initialization step signifies, that the simulation domain is initialized with a predetermined number of particles N_{gb} , calculated using Eq. (24). This calculation is based on the active volume for bead filling V_{act} , the bead filling degree ϕ , the porosity α , and the diameter of the grinding beads d_{gb} . The number is then rounded to the nearest integer value. The pore fraction value is assumed to be 0.41, which leads to a packing density factor of 0.59, representing loose random packing of spheres. The beads considered for the present study are yttrium-stabilized Zirconia beads. During the particle insertion, the stirrer is rotated for one rotation to disperse the particles in the computational domain. After the particle insertion into the domain, the

Fig. 2. Representation of the grinding chamber with stirrer of a bench scale, pin-type wet stirred media mill, MiniCer (Netzsch).

Table 4
Material properties and parameters used in the coupled CFD-DEM simulations.

Property	Symbol	Units	Value
Young's modulus	Y	GPa	1
Density (beads)	ρ_{gb}	$\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$	6050
Poisson's ratio	ν	–	0.31
Coefficient of restitution	e	–	0.92
Coefficient of static friction	μ_s	–	0.15
Coefficient of rolling friction	μ_r	–	0.01
Cut-off distance	d_{cut}	m	$0.05 d_{gb}$
Density (water)	ρ_f	$\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$	998.2
Viscosity (water)	η_f	mPa s	1.0016
Time step (DEM)	Δt_{DEM}	s	1×10^{-6}
Time step (CFD)	Δt_{CFD}	s	1×10^{-6}
Coupling interval	–	–	10

simulation is restarted (with the user-defined rotation speed) from the previous state and is coupled with CFD with two-way coupling, i.e., the exchange of forces between particles to fluid and fluid to particles takes place (as described in Section 2.3). This step is continued for two more stirrer rotations until the system is assumed to be stabilized (when the total kinetic energy of the particles in the system remains relatively constant, see Appendix B). Then, the system is restarted again for one more stirrer rotation to collect the necessary data for post-processing.

$$N_{gb} = \frac{V_{act}\phi(1-\alpha)}{\frac{\pi}{6}d_{gb}^3} \quad (24)$$

We adopted the material parameters, such as coefficients of restitution, Poisson's ratios, and coefficients of friction, from a previous work [56]. The Young's modulus of the material is reduced by 2 orders of magnitude (i.e., divided by 210) for computational feasibility [57]. The change of Young's modulus value effects the stress frequency as seen in Fig. A.14(b) of Appendix A, but for the current analysis a reduced value is chosen, and is maintained the same for all the cases. All of the properties and parameters used in this study are tabulated in Table 4. Note that, the parameters of both bead-bead and bead-wall interactions are assumed same, as it is the same material. As described in Section 2.1.2, a (lower) cut-off distance was chosen to inhibit the lubrication force. This dissipation happens prior to the contact between bead-bead or bead-wall and is different to the dissipation happening during the contact. The choice of d_{cut} value in this work is produce stable simulations i.e., to avoid scenarios where a contact is established before the lubrication force is cut-off. A small value of d_{cut} can be chosen, but the DEM time-step has to be reduced accordingly. The chosen d_{cut} is in the order of (virtual) product particle scale.

The finite volume grid for CFD calculations is generated using *blockMesh* and *snappyHexMesh* utilities of OpenFOAM-6 [36]. The mesh is generated such that most of the cells are hexahedrons with an average non-orthogonality of 13° . To be conservative, the CFD mesh is chosen such that the average edge length of the cells in the domain

are 2.5 to 3.0 times the bead diameter, i.e., $\Delta x \leq 2.5 - 3.0d_{gb}$ [58]. A smoothing length, $\lambda = 3d_{gb}$ (as described in Section 2.3.2) is chosen to account for the field smothering of cells with smaller edge lengths. The mesh was kept constant for all the simulation cases. We chose the $k - \epsilon$ turbulence model to account for fluid turbulence, as adopted in previous simulation studies for wet stirred media mills [13,23].

The time step of DEM is chosen as a fraction of the Rayleigh time step criterion given by,

$$\Delta t_{DEM} = a\Delta t_{Rayleigh} = a\frac{\pi}{2}d_{gb}\sqrt{\frac{\rho_{gb}}{G}} \left(\frac{1}{0.1631\nu + 0.8766} \right) \quad (25)$$

where a is a constant < 1 and $G = \frac{Y}{2(2+\nu)(1-\nu)}$ is the shear modulus (with Y the Young's modulus and ν the Poisson's ratio). In the present work, a conservative value of $a \leq 0.2$ is taken for stability.

For the CFD time-step (with an implicit scheme for viscous term of the VANS equations), the Courant–Friedrich–Lewy (CFL) [59] criterion leads to:

$$CFL = \Delta t_{CFD} \max \left(\frac{|u|}{\Delta x} \right) < 1 \quad (26)$$

where u is the fluid velocity and Δx is the edge length of a cell in the CFD grid. In all the cases of the current work, it was ensured that this value never exceeds 0.9, and it was indeed one of the stopping criteria for all simulations.

3.2.1. Investigated parameters

Different parameter sets were assessed with combination of process parameters i.e., stirrer rotation speed (n), bead diameter (d_{gb}), filling degree (ϕ). Also, the effect of fluid is assessed using the properties of water and glycerol mixtures, whose reference values are adopted from the literature [60,61].

- Diameter of the grinding beads: $d_{gb} = 800 \mu\text{m}$, and $1100 \mu\text{m}$.
- Stirrer rotation speed: $n = 2000 \text{ rpm}$, 2500 rpm , 3000 rpm , and 4000 rpm . The tip speeds translate to, $v_t = 6.18 \text{ m/s}$, 7.72 m/s , 9.27 m/s , and 12.36 m/s , respectively.
- Filling degree: $\phi = 0.6, 0.7$, and 0.8 , which translates to the number of grinding beads in the system (calculated using Eq. (24)).
- Fluid viscosity and density (at $T = 25^\circ\text{C}$) are according to the values shown in Table 5.

3.3. Post-processing

According to Kwade's stress model [2,62], which highlights the importance of stress frequency and stress energies in a WSMM, the stress energy (of the grinding beads) and stress frequency of the system

Table 5

Water, and Water + Glycerol properties [60,61] used in the coupled CFD-DEM simulations (at $T = 25$ °C).

% of Water, Glycerol [v/v]	Viscosity [mPas]	Density [$\frac{kg}{m^3}$]
100, 0	1.0016	998.2
75, 25	2.094	1069.5
50, 50	6.8559	1139.3
25, 75	41.295	1202.4

at different operating conditions follow the relations given by Eqs. (27) and (28), respectively.

$$SE_{gb} \propto d_{gb}^3 \cdot \rho_{gb} \cdot v_t^2 \quad (27)$$

where, SE_{gb} is a measure of the maximum stress energy in the mill (that is different to the mean stress energy in the system (\overline{SE}_{gb}), because of different stress energies of grinding beads in the system due to their spatial relative velocity distribution). d_{gb} is the diameter of the grinding beads, ρ_{gb} is their density, and v_t is the tip speed of the stirrer.

$$SF = \frac{N_c}{t} \propto n \cdot N_{gb} \quad (28)$$

where, $\frac{N_c}{t}$ is the number of contacts per unit time, and N_{gb} is the number of grinding beads in the system given by Eq. (24).

Therefore, the relevant data for evaluating a WSMM's behavior is the Stress Frequency (SF) and Stress Energy (SE), which in a combined form yield a stress energy distribution, for a given set of parameters in a simulation. In this work, this information is evaluated using the collisional kinetic energies in the system i.e., is the maximum transferable energy, calculated at the first contact of the two colliding entities [13] (bead-bead or bead-wall) in the system (see Eq. (29)).

$$SE_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot m^* \cdot v_{rel}^2 \quad (29)$$

where, SE_{ij} is the stress energy of a collision event involving the entities i and j , m^* is the equivalent mass of the entities involved in a collision (i.e., $\frac{1}{m^*} = \frac{1}{m_1} + \frac{1}{m_2}$, with m_1, m_2 being the masses of two entities in a collision; $m_1 = m_2 = m_{gb}$ for a bead-bead collision and $m_1 = m_{gb}, m_2 = \infty$ for a bead-wall collision). v_{rel} is the relative velocity of two colliding entities.

In this work, the stress energies are calculated using the sum of energies from all contact modes in a collision (shown in Fig. 3), adopted from the work of Beinert et al. [13], described as an extended contact analysis. The corresponding equation for summation of the energies across the contact modes is given in Eq. (30). In the results, the total stress energy (Eq. (30)) of each collision is represented, the mean (or average) stress energy and stress frequency are calculated for the same. For all stress energy distributions, every decade is logarithmic equally spaced into 100 intervals, i.e., a total of 2000 intervals with the lowest limit translating to 10^{-20} J.

$$SE_{ij} = m^* \left[\frac{1}{2} (\bar{v}_{n,rel})^2 + \frac{1}{5} r^2 (\bar{\omega}_{n,rel})^2 + \frac{1}{2} (\bar{v}_{s1} - \bar{v}_{s2})^2 + \frac{1}{5} r^2 (\bar{\omega}_{s1} - \bar{\omega}_{s2})^2 + \frac{1}{2} (\bar{v}_{r1} + \bar{v}_{r2})^2 + \frac{1}{5} r^2 (\bar{\omega}_{r1} + \bar{\omega}_{r2})^2 \right] \quad (30)$$

where, the \bar{v} and $\bar{\omega}$ indicate the translational and rotational velocity vectors respectively. The subscripts n, s , and r represent the normal, shearing and rolling modes, respectively (as illustrated in Fig. 3).

In the post-processing step, the mean stress energy and the stress frequency of a stress energy distribution are calculated as follows:

$$\overline{SE} = \sum_{l=1}^{N_l=2000} SE_l \cdot p_l \quad (31)$$

$$SF = \sum_{l=1}^{N_l=2000} N_{c,l} \quad (32)$$

Fig. 3. Possible ideal contact types and the corresponding directions of translational and rotational velocities (according to Beinert et al. [13]). The subscripts t, n, r, and s represent the translational, normal, rolling and shearing modes respectively.

where \overline{SE} and SF are the mean stress energy, and stress frequency respectively. N_l is the number of stress energy classes (taken as 2000). SE_l and p_l are the magnitude and probability density of the stress energy class l , respectively. $N_{c,l}$ is the number of stress events in class l .

4. Results and discussion

4.1. DEM vs coupled CFD-DEM comparison

In order to analyze the influence of the modeling considerations, such as the need for CFD-DEM coupling and lubrication forces, a few cases were setup with a stirrer tip speed of 9.27 m/s, a bead diameter of 1100 μm , and a filling degree of 0.8 ($N_{gb} = 135455$). Also, the fluid properties are varied in a few cases to identify their influence. Here, we use the same approach as described in Section 3.2: initializing particles with one stirrer rotation (DEM), followed by system stabilization and run with two and one stirrer rotations (coupled CFD-DEM), respectively. Note that the stress frequency here indicates the number of collision events per time of one rotation.

Fig. 4 illustrates the comparisons of results from different DEM and coupled CFD-DEM simulations. Fig. 4(a) shows the comparison of the cases with only DEM. It can be seen that there was no significant difference between the trends of DEM and DEM with lubrication (at low viscosity). However, it can be observed that the stress energy distribution in the case of DEM with lubrication (at high viscosity) shifts towards smaller stressing energies, indicating the increase in dampening of collision intensities. This implies that when the viscosity is increased, the lubrication force increases, leading to a slow down of the relative velocities between the bead-bead and bead-wall approach, as also experienced and described by Knieke et al. [63].

Fig. 4(b) shows the comparison of the cases with DEM and coupled CFD-DEM with no lubrication effect. The distributions show a clear difference for DEM only and coupled CFD-DEM cases. This is due to the fact that the presence of fluid in the system provides a better dispersion and enhanced transfer of power input i.e., from the stirrer to beads via the fluid. It can be observed that the cases with different fluid properties are almost identical for the stress frequency values, with a subtle difference in the overall distribution (shifted to higher stress

Fig. 4. Stress energy distributions showcasing the system behavior at various model considerations. (a) DEM only, (b) DEM and coupled CFD-DEM comparison without lubrication effect, (c) Coupled CFD-DEM comparison with and without lubrication effect, (d) DEM and coupled CFD-DEM comparison. All the cases were setup with the stirrer tip speed of 9.27 m/s, bead diameter of 1100 μm , and a filling degree of 80% ($N_{gb} = 135455$).

energies). One might expect that there will be a higher difference in the stress energy distributions for such change in fluid properties. However, without considering lubrication a significant higher portion of bead contacts with stress energies $> 10^{-5}$ J occur (the log scale is somewhat attenuates this difference).

Fig. 4(c) compares the cases of coupled CFD-DEM with and without lubrication effect. For the cases with water properties, there was no pronounced change in the stress energy distributions and the distributions are identical. However, in the case of changed fluid properties (water-glycerol mixture), there is a decrease in the stress frequency, and also the distribution is shifted to smaller stress energies. This indicates the expected change in the system behavior due to increased contact damping by the modified fluid properties. This analysis shows the need for inclusion of the lubrication force, especially when an unresolved CFD-DEM coupling is used, and fluids with medium or high viscosity are modeled.

Finally, Fig. 4(d) describes the overall effect of different considerations of DEM, coupled CFD-DEM, and lubrication forces. In conclusion, we are convinced that the correct simulation of WSMM's requires a sufficient CFD-DEM coupling and, at least for the suspensions having viscosities higher than water, an adequate consideration of the lubrication effect. Consequently, all further simulations have been carried out using CFD-DEM coupling with lubrication effect.

4.2. Bead velocity distribution

The bead velocity distribution in Fig. 5 illustrates that a chunk of the grinding beads are observed to accumulate at the mill's right end, exhibiting low velocities i.e., insufficiently agitated for an effective grinding contribution. Therefore, for the comparisons in the following

Fig. 5. Instantaneous bead velocity distribution at the end of the simulation. Case: $v_t = 9.26$ m/s, $d_{gb} = 1100$ μm , and $\phi = 0.8$.

section, the events with low stress energies are excluded from the stress energy distribution, and the system's characteristics are compared using a truncated distribution, i.e., applying a lower threshold of 10^{-7} J (adopted from Stender et al. [8]).

4.3. Effect of operating parameters

Fig. 6 describes the change in system behavior when the process parameters are changed, such as stirrer tip speed, bead diameter, and filling degree. Fig. 6(a) illustrates the change of mean stress energy of

Fig. 6. Comparison of the system behavior at different operating conditions i.e., stirrer tip speed, bead diameter, filling degree, but at a constant viscosity of 1.0016 mPas. (a) Comparison of mean stress energy of the system, (b) Comparison of stress frequency of the system.

the system. It can be seen that the mean stress energy increases with increase in stirrer tip speed. This is obvious as the increase in tip speed introduces more power or energy, respectively into the system, which transfers from stirrer to the fluid (and grinding beads), and from the fluid to the grinding beads. With the decrease in bead diameter (size), the mean stress energy is reduced, as smaller beads have less inertia compared to the larger beads, resulting in less intense collisions, as already shown by Eq. (27). However, a change of filling degree (for a specific bead diameter) did not affect the mean stress energy of the system, which aligns with the relation described in Eq. (27), as it has no dependence on the filling degree or number of particles in the system.

Fig. 6(b) illustrates the change of stress frequency of the system. It is evident that the stress frequency is a function of both stirrer tip speed and the bead number, as described in Eq. (28). The increase is in the order of ~ 591 million collisions per second for the lowest and highest speed settings, i.e., 6.18 m/s and 12.36 m/s, respectively, for bead diameter of 1100 μm and 80% filling degree. However, for the 800 μm bead diameter, the increase is in the order of ~ 2.39 billion collisions per second. In contrast to the mean stress energy, the stress frequency increases with a decrease in bead diameter due to the increased number of beads in the system (increase in bead filling degree) as given by Eq. (28).

In order to compare the system behavior to the trends seen in Kwade [62] and Beinert et al. [13], a non-linear regression analysis is performed on the extracted stress energies to evaluate the fitting coefficients. Figs. 7, 8 & 9 show the comparison of regression fits of \overline{SE} , SE_{90} , and SF , respectively, with the fitting equations from Kwade [62] and Beinert et al. [13]. Figs. 7 & 8 indicate high R^2 values for all the fitting equations. The SE_{90} data fit, which corresponds to the maximum stress energy in the a WSMM, has similar fitting coefficients as compared to Kwade's fit [62]. Also, the data fit coefficients in Fig. 9, which represents the stress frequency estimation, match well with the coefficients in Kwade's fit [62]. The low R^2 value (in Fig. 9) of Beinert's fit is because the fitting coefficients (described in Beinert et al. [13]) are from the consideration of the entire stress energy distribution instead of the truncated distribution i.e., the ineffective events with low stress energy were also considered (see Appendix C for the regression analysis with complete stress energy distribution).

4.4. Change of the fluid properties

The effect of change in system behavior due to the alteration of fluid properties is investigated by adjusting fluid viscosity and density values, as described in Table 5. The simulations for this analysis are

Fig. 7. \overline{SE} comparison to the fitting equations. The trends include a non-linear regression fit, equations given in Kwade [62], and Beinert et al. [13].

Fig. 8. SE_{90} comparison to the fitting equations. The trends include a non-linear regression fit, equations given in Kwade [62], and Beinert et al. [13].

carried out with a filling degree of 0.7 and a stirrer tip speed of 6.18 m/s using 1100 μm beads. Fig. 10 shows the entire stress energy distribution of different water-glycerol mixtures. It can be seen that the distribution

Fig. 9. SF comparison to the fitting equations. The trends include a non-linear regression fit, equations given in Kwade [62], and Beinert et al. [13].

Fig. 10. Stress energy distributions from simulations with different fluid properties, according to Table 5.

has significant change when the percentage of Glycerol is the highest. This shows that the change in fluid properties will indeed effect the system dynamics (especially for medium to high viscosities).

The change in the stress frequency due to the fluid properties (indicated by the percentage of glycerol present in water by volume) is depicted in Fig. 11(a). An increase in the viscosity (and corresponding density) of the fluid decreases the stress frequency. This can be understood by the fact that the movement of beads dispersed in a viscous fluid is compromised, which results a drop in the stress frequency. The mean stress energy of the system stayed relatively constant for all cases.

To further analyze the stress frequency dependency, we calculate the dimensionless numbers such as Power and Reynolds numbers based on the fluid properties and system response, using Eqs. (33) and (34), respectively.

$$N_p = \frac{2\pi\Gamma}{\rho_f n^2 D^5} \quad (33)$$

$$Re = \frac{\rho_f D^2 n}{\eta_f} \quad (34)$$

Here, n is the characteristic rotational speed, D is the characteristic length (stirrer diameter), ρ_f is the fluid density, and η_f is its dynamic viscosity. Γ represents the total torque acting on the stirrer (i.e., torque due to particles + torque due to fluid interaction), which is calculated from the simulations.

Fig. 11. Effect of fluid properties i.e., fluid viscosity and density. (a) Fluid properties effect on the mean stress energy (left) and stress frequency (right), (b) Comparison of dimensionless numbers and their potential relation with stress frequency. All cases are at 0.7 filling degree, stirrer tip speed of 6.18 m/s with 1100 μ m beads.

Fig. 12. Power on the stirrer versus numerical power, where the active power transferred to the particles is compared to the overall power transferred into the mill.

Fig. 11(b) shows the relation of Power Number and Stress Frequency with respect to the Reynolds Number, and a potential relation connecting the two dimensionless numbers to the stress frequency is illustrated.

4.5. Stirrer power vs numerical power

To determine the mill-related energy transfer, i.e., the power transferred from the stirrer to the grinding beads, we compare the power

Fig. 13. Instantaneous bead velocity distribution (a slice at the mill center) at the end of the simulation. (a) at tip speed of 6.18 m/s, (b) at tip speed of 9.27 m/s, both with 1100 μm beads and 80% filling degree.

on the stirrer ($P_s = 2\pi n\Gamma$) with the numerical power calculated using the mean stress energy and stress frequency values ($P_{gb} = SE_{gb} \cdot SF_{gb}$). The values are plotted in Fig. 12. The relation of P_s and P_{gb} (in Fig. 12) can be expressed as a potential function (with an exponent of 2.8, $R^2 = 0.987$), as they have a linear relation on log–log plot. It can be seen that the energy transfer increases with an increase in rotation speed and also with bead filling degree.

It turns out that about 15% of the energy is transferred to the product particles at small power inputs (at low tip speeds) up to 50% at high tip speeds. This means that the beads move more efficient at high tip speeds. This observation could be motivated by looking at the bead velocity distributions in Fig. 13, where it is seen that at a higher tip speed (Fig. 13(b)), the beads are well agitated and the activation seems much better than at the lower tip speed (Fig. 13(a)). This, therefore, could be a reason for the enhanced energy transfer at high tip speeds.

5. Conclusion and future outlook

In this study, we present a detailed simulation of a pin-type wet stirred media mill using a coupled CFD-DEM framework. Modeling considerations such as, the need for CFD-DEM coupling, and the role of lubrication forces, are highlighted by comparing the stress energy distributions. It was identified that the lubrication forces are needed to compensate for the unresolved CFD-DEM coupling approach (adopted in this work), especially for medium to high viscous fluids.

In comparison to the original stressing model (from Kwade [62]), this modeling framework describes the entirety of the stress energy distribution of the system (similar to the work from Beinert et al. [13]). The effect of process parameters such as stirrer rotation speed, bead diameter, and filling degree, on the system behavior align with the trends observed in the literature. But, it is important to correctly post-process the stress energy distributions for such comparison. In this work, a threshold value of 10^{-7} J [8] was applied on the stress energy distributions to do so. Furthermore, the stress frequency dependency on the fluid properties was identified by analyzing the water–glycerol mixtures. But in a real grinding scenario, the behavior of the suspension can change from Newtonian to non-Newtonian, depending on the material used. In the case of non-Newtonian fluids, the viscosity is dependent also on the shear rate.

The immersed boundary methodology adopted in the current study (Section 2.3.3) provides flexibility to model and simulate arbitrarily shaped stirrer geometries. This approach allows for the virtual analysis and assessment of new stirrer designs.

A calibration and validation methodology is needed to fine-tune the simulation parameters such that the simulation results can be effectively compared with the real-world data. Analyses such as grid dependence and the choice of turbulence model should be explored for validation purposes. As demonstrated in our current work, both fluid properties and DEM parameters (Appendix A) have a notable

impact on system behavior. These findings provide a foundational understanding of potential and effective options for parameterizing and adjusting the system. Once calibrated, the simulation data can serve as a valuable input for the predictive models, such as population balance modeling. These models can subsequently be used to evaluate grinding performance and make informed decisions about process optimization.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Yeswanth Sai Tanneru: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jan Henrik Finke:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Carsten Schilde:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Yogesh M. Harshe:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Arno Kwade:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Sensitivity analysis of DEM parameters

A sensitivity analysis is performed to identify the influence of DEM parameters on the system behavior. For this purpose, coupled CFD-DEM simulations were analyzed by varying the contact parameters in DEM such as coefficient of restitution (e), coefficients of friction (μ_s, μ_r), and a material parameter Young's modulus Y . The fluid properties were kept constant for this analysis with $\eta_f = 1.0016$ mPa s and $\rho_f = 998.2$ $\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$.

Fig. A.14. Stress energy distributions from the sensitivity analysis using the DEM parameter sets from Table A.6. (a) Effect of coefficient of restitution, (b) Effect of Young's modulus, (c) Effect of sliding friction coefficient (set-I, Table A.6), (d) Effect of sliding friction coefficient (set-II, Table A.6), (e) Effect of rolling friction coefficient (set-I, Table A.6), (f) Effect of rolling friction coefficient (set-II, Table A.6)

All the simulations operated with $1100 \mu\text{m}$ beads, a stirrer tip speed of 9.27 m/s , and a filling degree of 0.8.

A set of simulations was considered, and the DEM parameters were varied, using a standard case as a basis. The changes and simulation nomenclature are described in Table A.6. Two sets of simulations are derived, one with a high coefficient of restitution and the other set with a reduced coefficient of restitution. Fig. A.14(a) shows the effect of change in coefficient of restitution on the system behavior. It can be seen that there is a pronounced decrease in the stress frequency when the coefficient of restitution is reduced, and the distribution shifts left

when the coefficient of restitution is changed from 0.92 to 0.5 while there was no significant shift for a change from 0.5 to 0.01.

Fig. A.14(b) shows the effect of Young's modulus on the system behavior. In this case, the stress frequency of the distribution is reduced with the reduced Young's modulus, which appears more pronounced when compared to the case where the coefficient of restitution is decreased (i.e., $Y = 1 \text{ GPa}$; standard case in set-II).

Figs. A.14(c) & A.14(d) show the influence of the sliding friction on the system behavior. In Fig. A.14(c), the increase in μ_s has decreased the stress frequency with no considerable shift (up until $\mu_s = 0.3$), and

Table A.6

Sets of DEM parameters considered for sensitivity analysis to evaluate their influence on the system behavior.

Set - I				
Case	μ_s	e	Y	μ_r
Standard	0.1	0.92	1 GPa	0.01
Soft	0.1	0.92	0.1 GPa	0.01
Inelastic	0.1	0.01	1 GPa	0.01
Medium μ_r	0.1	0.92	1 GPa	0.3
High μ_r	0.1	0.92	1 GPa	1
Medium μ_s	0.3	0.92	1 GPa	0.01
High μ_s	0.9	0.92	1 GPa	0.01
Set - II				
Case	μ_s	e	Y	μ_r
Standard	0.1	0.5	1 GPa	0.01
Soft	0.1	0.5	0.1 GPa	0.01
Inelastic	0.1	0.01	1 GPa	0.01
Medium μ_r	0.1	0.5	1 GPa	0.3
High μ_r	0.1	0.5	1 GPa	1
Medium μ_s	0.3	0.5	1 GPa	0.01
High μ_s	0.9	0.5	1 GPa	0.01

Fig. B.1. Total kinetic energy of the beads with respect to simulation run-time. Purple and green trends indicate the stable (2 rotations), and run (1 rotation) steps, respectively. **Case:** 1100 μm beads at 6.18 m/s, with 80% bead filling.

the distribution shifted right for $\mu_s = 0.9$. As seen in Fig. A.14(d), the effect of reduction in stress frequency was not so pronounced i.e., for cases in set-II, when the coefficient of restitution is decreased to 0.5. And, a similar trend in the shift of the distribution can be seen here.

Figs. A.14(e) & A.14(f) show the influence of the rolling friction on the system behavior. In both the cases, it can be seen that there is a slight reduction in the stress frequency when μ_r is increased from 0.01 to 0.3, and the effect completely vanished when μ_r is further increased to 1 resulting in an identical distribution (same as $\mu_r = 0.3$).

In conclusion, the chosen parameter sets (in Table A.6) evaluate the range DEM parameters that can be applied in a WSMM simulation. In this analysis, a higher value for Young's Modulus is not included for computational feasibility. Results indicate that the system behavior indeed changes by changing the DEM parameter sets. The simulation framework presented in this work needs a calibration procedure (similar to Cabiscol et al. [22]) to accurately capture the real system behavior. While fluid properties play an important role in determining the stress energies and stress frequencies, it is important to also include the interactions of grinding beads when (virtual) product particles are present. A potential possibility is to adjust the DEM parameters to represent the bulk behavior (with virtual product particles).

Fig. B.2. \overline{SE} comparison to the fitting equations. The trends include a non-linear regression fit, equations given in Kwade [62], and Beinert et al. [13].

Fig. B.3. SE_{90} comparison to the fitting equations. The trends include a non-linear regression fit, equations given in Kwade [62], and Beinert et al. [13].

Appendix B. Total kinetic energy of the particles

Fig. B.1 shows the evolution of total kinetic energy of the particles (in DEM) with respect to simulation run-time. The results indicate that the adopted system is relatively stable after two stirrer rotations.

Appendix C. Regression analysis with complete stress energy distribution

This section shows the comparisons of \overline{SE} , SE_{90} , and SF when the complete stress energy distribution is considered, instead of a truncated distribution i.e, with a lower threshold for stress energy (as assumed in Section 4.3).

Figs. B.2, B.3 & B.4 show the comparisons of \overline{SE} , SE_{90} , and SF , respectively. Although the fitting equations for \overline{SE} and SE_{90} in Figs. B.2 & B.3, respectively, have a high R^2 values, the fitting equation of Kwade [62] (in Fig. B.4) does not agree with the data fit. The coefficient for rotation speed in the regression analysis (denoted as data fit) is relatively small, indicating a lower dependence of stress frequency on the stirrer rotation speed.

Fig. B.4. SF comparison to the fitting equations. The trends include a non-linear regression fit, equations given in Kwade [62], and Beinert et al. [13].

References

- [1] E. Bilgili, G. Guner, Mechanistic modeling of wet stirred media milling for production of drug nanosuspensions, *AAPS PharmSciTech* 22 (2021) 1–23.
- [2] A. Kwade, J. Schwedes, Wet grinding in stirred media mills, *Handb. Powder Technol.* 12 (2007) 251–382.
- [3] N. Matsanga, W. Nheta, N. Chimwani, A review of the grinding media in ball mills for mineral processing, *Minerals* 13 (11) (2023) 1373.
- [4] S. Mende, F. Stenger, W. Peukert, J. Schwedes, Mechanical production and stabilization of submicron particles in stirred media mills, *Powder Technol.* 132 (1) (2003) 64–73.
- [5] M. Nöske, S. Breitung-Faes, A. Kwade, Electrostatic stabilization and characterization of fine ground silicon particles in ethanol, *Silicon* 11 (2019) 3001–3010.
- [6] S. Breitung-Faes, A. Kwade, Prediction of energy effective grinding conditions, *Miner. Eng.* 43 (2013) 36–43.
- [7] F. Flach, S. Breitung-Faes, A. Kwade, Model based process optimization of nanosuspension preparation via wet stirred media milling, *Powder Technol.* 331 (2018) 146–154.
- [8] H.H. Stender, A. Kwade, J. Schwedes, Stress energy distribution in different stirred media mill geometries, *Int. J. Miner. Process.* 74 (2004) S103–S117.
- [9] F. Flach, S. Breitung-Faes, A. Kwade, Scaling wet fine grinding processes of organic particles using stirred media mills, *Chem. Ing. Tech.* 89 (8) (2017) 1051–1059.
- [10] R.M. de Carvalho, T.M. Campos, P.M. Faria, L.M. Tavares, Mechanistic modeling and simulation of grinding iron ore pellet feed in pilot and industrial-scale ball mills, *Powder Technol.* 392 (2021) 489–502.
- [11] R.M. de Carvalho, L.M. Tavares, Predicting the effect of operating and design variables on breakage rates using the mechanistic ball mill model, *Miner. Eng.* 43 (2013) 91–101.
- [12] A.L. de Oliveira, R.M. de Carvalho, L.M. Tavares, Predicting the effect of operating and design variables in grinding in a vertical stirred mill using a mechanistic mill model, *Powder Technol.* 387 (2021) 560–574.
- [13] S. Beinert, G. Fragnière, C. Schilde, A. Kwade, Analysis and modelling of bead contacts in wet-operating stirred media and planetary ball mills with CFD–DEM simulations, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 134 (2015) 648–662.
- [14] C. Thon, A.C. Böttcher, F. Möhlen, M. Yu, A. Kwade, C. Schilde, Multi-modal framework to model wet milling through numerical simulations and artificial intelligence (part 1), *Chem. Eng. J.* 449 (2022) 137794.
- [15] C. Thon, A.C. Böttcher, F. Möhlen, M. Yu, A. Kwade, C. Schilde, Multi-modal framework to model wet milling through numerical simulations and artificial intelligence (part 2), *Chem. Eng. J.* 450 (2022) 137947.
- [16] P.W. Cleary, M. Sinnott, R. Morrison, Prediction of slurry transport in SAG mills using SPH fluid flow in a dynamic DEM based porous media, *Miner. Eng.* 19 (15) (2006) 1517–1527.
- [17] C. Ndimande, P. Cleary, A. Mainza, M. Sinnott, Using two-way coupled DEM–SPH to model an industrial scale stirred media detritator, *Miner. Eng.* 137 (2019) 259–276.
- [18] P.W. Cleary, M.D. Sinnott, Computational prediction of performance for a full scale isamill: Part 2–wet models of charge and slurry transport, *Miner. Eng.* 79 (2015) 239–260.
- [19] P. Jonsén, S. Hammarberg, B.I. Pålsson, G. Lindkvist, Preliminary validation of a new way to model physical interactions between pulp, charge and mill structure in tumbling mills, *Miner. Eng.* 130 (2019) 76–84.
- [20] S. Larsson, B.I. Pålsson, M. Parian, P. Jonsén, A novel approach for modelling of physical interactions between slurry, grinding media and mill structure in wet stirred media mills, *Miner. Eng.* 148 (2020) 106180.
- [21] S. Larsson, J.M. Rodríguez Prieto, H. Heiskari, P. Jonsén, A novel particle-based approach for modeling a wet vertical stirred media mill, *Minerals* 11 (1) (2021) 55.
- [22] R. Cabisco, T. Jansen, M. Marigo, C. Ness, Application of hydrodynamic lubrication in discrete element method (DEM) simulations of wet bead milling chambers, *Powder Technol.* 384 (2021) 542–553.
- [23] G. Fragnière, A. Naumann, M. Schrader, A. Kwade, C. Schilde, Grinding media motion and collisions in different zones of stirred media mills, *Minerals* 11 (2) (2021) 185.
- [24] K.J. Berger, C.M. Hrenya, Challenges of DEM: II. Wide particle size distributions, *Powder Technol.* 264 (2014) 627–633.
- [25] D. Jajcevic, E. Siegmund, C. Radeke, J.G. Khinast, Large-scale CFD–DEM simulations of fluidized granular systems, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 98 (2013) 298–310.
- [26] G. Fragnière, S. Beinert, A. Overbeck, I. Kampen, C. Schilde, A. Kwade, Predicting effects of operating condition variations on breakage rates in stirred media mills, *Chem. Eng. Res. Des.* 138 (2018) 433–443.
- [27] S. Beinert, C. Schilde, A. Kwade, Simulation of Stress Energy and Grinding Media Movement within a Wet-Operated Annular-Gap Mill Using the Discrete-Element Method, *Chemical engineering & technology* 35 (11) (2012) 1911–1921.
- [28] R.H. Davis, J.M. Serrayssol, E. Hinch, The elastohydrodynamic collision of two spheres, *J. Fluid Mech.* 163 (1986) 479–497.
- [29] R.M. de Carvalho, A.L. Oliveira, H.A. Petit, L.M. Tavares, Comparing modeling approaches in simulating a continuous pilot-scale wet vertical stirred mill using PBM–DEM–CFD, *Adv. Powder Technol.* 34 (9) (2023) 104135.
- [30] B. Blais, M. Lassaingne, C. Goniva, L. Fradette, F. Bertrand, Development of an unresolved CFD–DEM model for the flow of viscous suspensions and its application to solid–liquid mixing, *J. Comput. Phys.* 318 (2016) 201–221.
- [31] B. Blais, M. Lassaingne, C. Goniva, L. Fradette, F. Bertrand, A semi-implicit immersed boundary method and its application to viscous mixing, *Comput. Chem. Eng.* 85 (2016) 136–146.
- [32] M. Kroupa, M. Vonka, M. Soos, J. Kosek, Utilizing the discrete element method for the modeling of viscosity in concentrated suspensions, *Langmuir* 32 (33) (2016) 8451–8460.
- [33] C. Kloss, C. Goniva, A. Hager, S. Amberger, S. Pirker, Models, algorithms and validation for opensource DEM and CFD–DEM, *Prog. Comput. Fluid Dyn.* 12 (2–3) (2012) 140–152.
- [34] LIGGGHTS, LIGGGHTS, LAMMPS improved for general granular and granular heat transfer simulations, 2023, URL: <https://github.com/ParticulateFlow/LIGGGHTS-PFM>. (Accessed 2023).
- [35] CFDEM, CFDEM- open source CFD, DEM and CFD–DEM, 2023, URL: <https://github.com/ParticulateFlow/CFDEMCoupling-PFM>. (Accessed 2023).
- [36] OpenFOAM, OpenFOAM- Open source field operation and manipulation, 2023, URL: <https://github.com/OpenFOAM/OpenFOAM-6>. (Accessed 2023).
- [37] P.A. Cundall, O.D. Strack, A discrete numerical model for granular assemblies, *Geotechnique* 29 (1) (1979) 47–65.
- [38] H.P. Zhu, Z.Y. Zhou, R. Yang, A. Yu, Discrete particle simulation of particulate systems: theoretical developments, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 62 (13) (2007) 3378–3396.
- [39] H. Hertz, Über die Berührung fester elastischer Körper, *J. Reine Angew. Math.* 92 (1881) 156.
- [40] K. Johnson, Normal contact of elastic solids: Hertz theory, *Contact Mech.* (1989) 84–106.
- [41] R.D. Mindlin, Compliance of Elastic Bodies in Contact, *American Society of Mechanical Engineers*, 1949.
- [42] R.D. Mindlin, H. Deresiewicz, Elastic Spheres in Contact Under Varying Oblique Forces, *American Society of Mechanical Engineers*, 1953.
- [43] J. Mewis, N.J. Wagner, *Colloidal Suspension Rheology*, Cambridge University Press, 2012.
- [44] S. Dance, M. Maxey, Incorporation of lubrication effects into the force-coupling method for particulate two-phase flow, *J. Comput. Phys.* 189 (1) (2003) 212–238.
- [45] O.I. Vinogradova, Drainage of a thin liquid film confined between hydrophobic surfaces, *Langmuir* 11 (6) (1995) 2213–2220.
- [46] Z. Zhou, S. Kuang, K. Chu, A. Yu, Discrete particle simulation of particle–fluid flow: model formulations and their applicability, *J. Fluid Mech.* 661 (2010) 482–510.
- [47] R.I. Issa, Solution of the implicitly discretised fluid flow equations by operator-splitting, *J. Comput. Phys.* 62 (1) (1986) 40–65.
- [48] C.T. Crowe, J.D. Schwarzkopf, M. Sommerfeld, Y. Tsuji, *Multiphase Flows with Droplets and Particles*, CRC Press, 2011.
- [49] D.L. Koch, R.J. Hill, Inertial effects in suspension and porous-media flows, *Annu. Rev. Fluid Mech.* 33 (1) (2001) 619–647.
- [50] M.S. Van Buijtenen, W.J. Van Dijk, N.G. Deen, J. Kuipers, T. Leadbeater, D. Parker, Numerical and experimental study on multiple-spout fluidized beds, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 66 (11) (2011) 2368–2376.
- [51] S. Beinert, G. Fragnière, C. Schilde, A. Kwade, Multiscale simulation of fine grinding and dispersing processes: Stressing probability, stressing energy and resultant breakage rate, *Adv. Powder Technol.* 29 (3) (2018) 573–583.

- [52] C. Goniva, C. Kloss, N.G. Deen, J.A. Kuipers, S. Pirker, Influence of rolling friction on single spout fluidized bed simulation, *Particuology* 10 (5) (2012) 582–591.
- [53] J. Marshall, K. Sala, Comparison of methods for computing the concentration field of a particulate flow, *Int. J. Multiph. Flow* 56 (2013) 4–14.
- [54] S. Pirker, D. Kahrmanovic, C. Goniva, Improving the applicability of discrete phase simulations by smoothing their exchange fields, *Appl. Math. Model.* 35 (5) (2011) 2479–2488.
- [55] H.E. Van den Akker, The details of turbulent mixing process and their simulation, *Adv. Chem. Eng.* 31 (2006) 151–229.
- [56] S. Beinert, C. Schilde, G. Gronau, A. Kwade, CFD-discrete element method simulations combined with compression experiments to characterize stirred-media mills, *Chem. Eng. Technol.* 37 (5) (2014) 770–778.
- [57] S. Lommen, D. Schott, G. Lodewijks, DEM speedup: Stiffness effects on behavior of bulk material, *Particuology* 12 (2014) 107–112.
- [58] Z. Wang, M. Liu, On the determination of grid size/smoothing distance in un-/semi-resolved CFD-DEM simulation of particulate flows, *Powder Technol.* 394 (2021) 73–82.
- [59] J.H. Ferziger, M. Perić, R.L. Street, *Computational Methods for Fluid Dynamics*, Springer, 2019.
- [60] N.S. Cheng, Formula for the viscosity of a glycerol-water mixture, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 47 (9) (2008) 3285–3288.
- [61] A. Volk, C.J. Kähler, Density model for aqueous glycerol solutions, *Exp. Fluids* 59 (5) (2018) 75.
- [62] A. Kwade, A stressing model for the description and optimization of grinding processes, *Chem. Eng. Technol. Ind. Chem. Plant Equip. Process. Eng. Biotechnol.* 26 (2) (2003) 199–205.
- [63] C. Knieke, C. Steinborn, S. Romeis, W. Peukert, S. Breitung-Faes, A. Kwade, Nanoparticle production with stirred-media mills: opportunities and limits, *Chem. Eng. Technol.* 33 (9) (2010) 1401–1411.